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LIPID LOWERING ACTIVITY OF A POLYHERBAL FORMULATION ON TRITON WR-1339 (TYLOXAPOL) INDUCED HYPERLIPIDEMIA IN WISTAR RATS

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ABSTRACT

We investigated the possible antihyperlipidemic activity of a hydroalcoholic extract of an herbal preparation from a combination of three Indian medicinal plants against Triton WR-1339 induced hyperlipidemia in male *Wistar* rats. The current study was undertaken to assess the hypolipidemic, hypocholesterolemic and hypotriglyceridemic potential of the Polyherbal Formulation (PHF) using Triton WR-1339 (Tyloxapol) induced hyperlipidemia. The male *Wistar* rats were divided into five groups of six animals in each group normal control, hyperlipidemic control, hyperlipidemic plus polyherbal extract and hyperlipidemic plus Atorvastatin. Hyperlipidemia was induced in overnight fasted *Wistar* rats by single intravenous (IV) injection of 200 mg/kg or 2ml/kg of Triton WR-1339 in Normal Saline (0.9% NaCl) and it showed sustained elevated levels of serum Total Cholesterol (TC), Triglyceride (TG), LDL-C and VLDL. The Polyherbal Formulation (200 and 400 mg/kg/b.w. /p.o.) and Atorvastatin (10 mg/kg/b.w. /p.o.) was administered orally for seven days to Triton WR-1339 induced hyperlipidemic rats. The PHF significantly decreased serum total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL-C, VLDL, Atherogenic Index and increased HDL-C levels. Atherogenic Index and Triglyceride and cholesterol secretion rate were lowered in the polyherbal extract fed animals when compared to hyperlipidemic control animals. Polyherbal extract exhibited quite competitive potential when compared with the reference drug Atorvastatin affording a possible alternative natural therapeutic agent in the treatment of hyperlipidemia. The present work provides scientific evidence of therapeutic potential of hydroalcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation against hyperlipidemia. Hence, we suggest that the inclusion of this PHF in the management of hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia.

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INTRODUCTION

Hyperlipidemia can be defined as elevation of serum Total Cholesterol (TC) and/or Triglyceride (TG) or reduced High Density Lipoprotein (HDL-C) cholesterol that predisposes to the development of Atherosclerosis. Cholesterol is a waxy fat protein made by the liver. It is essential for healthy cell membranes; brain functioning, hormone production and vitamin storage. But, when you have too much in your blood, it can build up on the walls of your arteries [1]. High cholesterol can cause atherosclerosis, a dangerous accumulation of cholesterol and other deposits on the walls of the coronary arteries. These deposits (plaques) can reduce blood flow through your arteries, which can cause complications, such as heart attack, carotid artery (Brain Stroke), chest pain (Angina) and other symptoms of coronary artery disease (Atherosclerosis) [2]. High cholesterol or 'bad' cholesterol contributes to 2.6 million deaths (4.5 % of total) and 29.7 million disability adjusted life years (DALYS), & of total DALYS worldwide. The main causes for high cholesterol are both an unhealthy lifestyle and/ or genes [3]. Elevated lipid levels result from increased absorption through the gut or through enhanced endogenous synthesis. Hence, hyperlipidemia can be reduced by two possible ways, viz., by blocking endogenous synthesis or by decreasing absorption. Both these factors can be evaluated in normal animals without artificial diets using Triton WR 1339 [4].

The lowering of lipids and cholesterol levels by drug or dietary interventions could reduce the risk of CHDs. The known lipid lowering drugs (Statins, fibrates, bile acid sequestrants, etc.) regulate the lipid metabolism by different mechanisms, but they also have many side effects such as heart valve problems, valvular diseases, high blood pressure, palpitations hyperuricemia, myalgia, insomnia, abdominal cramping, gastric irritation, diarrhea, dry skin and abnormal liver function [5 & 6]. Hence, there is an increased demand for newer herbal drugs with an ability to reduce or regulate serum TG and TC concentrations. Medicinal plants continue to provide valuable therapeutic agents, both in modern medicine and in traditional systems. Plants and many plants derived preparations have long been used as traditional remedies and in folklore medicine for the treatment of hyperlipidemia in many parts of the world. Recently, the search for appropriate antihyperlipidemic agents have been again focused on plants because of less toxicity, easy availability and easy absorption in the body that may be better treatment than currently used drugs [7].

The ingredients in the PHF have been reported to possess the bark, leaves, heartwood and roots of the *Anogeissus latifolia* plant is traditionally used for the treatment of dysentery, snakebite, leprosy, wounds and ulcers, skin diseases, jaundice and diabetes [8]. The roots of *Holostemma annularis* are useful in ophthalmopathy, orchitis, cough, burning sensation, stomachalgia, constipation, fever and tridoshas. The roots is also used in spermatorrhoea and reported to possess cooling, tonic and lactative properties [9 & 10]. *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Boraginaceae) reported as a medicinal herb widely used in traditional system of medicine to treat dysentery, snake bite and urinary diseases. It is useful in vitiated conditions of *Vata* and *Kapha*, arthralgia, inflammations, dyspepsia, diarrhea, dysentery, leprosy and skin diseases [11, 12, 13 & 14].

The ability of PHF to decrease serum cholesterol, triglycerides and lipids has been studied may be due to the presence of flavinoids, tannins, phenols, steroids and saponins as they have been previously reported to possess hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic actions respectively [15 & 16]. But the effect of PHF on hyperlipidemia induced by Triton WR-1339 has not yet been studied. Therefore, our study was an attempt to determine the potential of hydroalcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation in bringing about changes in various parameters of serum lipid profiles, viz. TG, TC, LDL-C, VLDL-C and HDL-C. In the present study, A Polyherbal formulation containing hydroalcoholic extracts of *Anogeissus latifolia* (Combretaceae), *Holostemma annularis* (Asclepiadaceae) and *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Boraginaceae) was selected for studying its antihyperlipidemic activity against Triton WR-1339 induced Hyperlipidemia in male *Wistar* rats. The present study was undertaken to investigate the anti-hyperlipidemic effect of hydroalcoholic extract polyherbal formulation prepared using the above three medicinal plants against Triton WR -1339 induced hyperlipidemia in *Wistar* rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and Preparation of Extract

Preparation of Polyherbal Formulation

The ingredients of *Holostemma annularis* (Roots), *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Whole plant) and *Anogeissus latifolia* (Bark) were individually dried in shade, powdered and equal portion from each fraction of plant powder was subjected at 60-70°C using mixture of ethanol and water (60: 40) in a Soxhlet apparatus and then filtered and filtrate was evaporated at 55°C in hot air oven. The finished formulation was a fine powder, greenish brown in color and then mixed in mentioned proportion with help of suspending agent.

Dose Selection

The polyherbal formulation of the three herbs (viz. *Holostemma annularis* (Roots), *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Whole plant) and *Anogeissus latifolia* (Bark) was prepared according to their effective doses. PHF was suspended in distilled water and administered orally at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg, *p.o.* at a constant volume of 0.5 ml/100g of bodyweight. This dose was selected on the basis of our preliminary studies. The control animals received only the vehicle in the same volume and through the same route.

Drugs and Chemicals

Atorvastatin used from (Zydus Cadila Pharmaceuticals Ltd. India), Tyloxapol (Triton WR-1339) was obtained from Sigma, St. Louis, MO., USA, the other chemicals and analytical reagents grade obtained from Sicra labs (Prasanthi Nagar, Hyderabad, Telangana, India)

Animals

Male *Wistar* rats (100-150 g) were used in the present study. The rats were group housed in polyacrylic cages (38 × 23 × 10 cm) with not more than 4 animals per cage and maintained under standardized condition (12/12 h light/dark cycle, 24^o.C) with free access to pellet food and water. The experiments and study protocols were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee; Smt. Sarojini Ramulamma College of pharmacy bearing the number is 51/01/C/CPCSEA/2013/002 and is in accordance with guidance of Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA).

Acute Toxicity Studies

Acute toxicity studies for the hydro alcoholic extract of PHF were conducted as per OECD-423[17]. The PHF were administered orally following OECD 423 guidelines to 3 *Wistar* male (M1-M3) and 3 female rats (F1-F3) using limit dose in three steps (viz; exposing 3 female rats in 1st step & 3 male rats in the 2nd step to a dose of 500; 2000 and 4000 mg/kg body weight) [18]. Further three male rats were taken up and weighed and marked for identification and same procedure was repeated. Following administration of single dose of PHF animals were observed for the clinical symptoms for 30 minutes, at hourly intervals for next 24 hours (with special attention given during the first 4 hours) and daily thereafter, for a total of 14 days. All observations and results were systematically recorded with individual records being maintained for each animal. Observations included changes in skin, mortality and general behavioral pattern. Attention was given for observations of tremors, convulsions, depression, excitement, circling, salivation, diarrhea, lethargy, sleep and coma. No (Mortality) death was observed till the end of study. Body weight was recorded at 0, 7th and 14 day. The hydro alcoholic extract of PHF was found to be safe up to 4000 mg/kg body weight. Hence from the present study it can be concluded that PHF at the limit dose of 4000 mg/kg body weight.

Triton WR-1339 induced hyperlipidemia [19&20].

Male *Wistar* rats 150-200 gm. weight, were fasted for 18 hours and then injected intravenously freshly prepared solution of 200 mg/kg Triton WR-1339 (Isooctyl- Polyoxy-Ethylene Phenol) in normal saline. Serum cholesterol levels increase sharply 2-3 times after 24 h (Phase-I). The animals were administered test drugs employed (PHF 200 & 400 mg/k.g. /b.w. /p.o.), Standard drug Atorvastatin (10 mg/k.g/b.w. /p.o.) and solvent for the controls orally by Intragastric tube once daily for seven consecutive days. On 8th day, the animals were fasted for 18 hrs(had only access to water) and Triton WR 1339 was injected intravenously. Serum cholesterol and triglycerides analyses were made 24 hours after Triton injection. The systemic administration of the surfactant Triton to mice or rats results in a biphasic elevation of plasma cholesterol and triglycerides. [21].

Experimental Design

Male *Wistar* rats were divided into five groups of six animals in each group and were treated with single dose/day (*p.o.*) of standard drug or extracts. The first group (Normal Control) received normal saline 0.9% w/v orally for one week. The second group (Triton Positive Control) received Triton WR-1339 dissolved in 0.9% w/v saline (200 mg/kg, b.w.) by i.v. route. The third and fourth groups was administered a daily dose of Poly Herbal Formulation (200 and 400 mg/k.g/b.w. /p.o.) respectively, once in a day for one week. The fifth group was treated with Atorvastatin 10 mg/kg/b.w. once in a day for one week (Served as Standard). Saline, polyherbal extract and Atorvastatin were administered orally by Intragastric tube once daily for seven consecutive days. On the 8th day, the animals were starved for 18 hrs (had only access to water) and then injected intravenously freshly prepared solution of 200 mg/kg/b.w Triton WR-1339 (Isooctyl- Polyoxy-Ethylene Phenol) in normal saline, to all the four groups rats. Serum cholesterol levels increase sharply 2-3 times after 24 h (Phase-I) Triton injection. Blood was collected at 24 hr after Triton injection by Retro - Orbital Sinus Puncture, under mild Ether anesthesia. The collected blood samples were centrifuged using semi ultra-cooling centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes at room temperature and were directly used for estimating various biochemical tests (Serum Cholesterol, Triglycerides, LDL-C and HDL-C). All samples were stored at 4^oC until analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Turkey test and $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM for six rats per group.

RESULTS

Acute Toxicity Studies

No (Mortality) death was observed till the end of study. Body weight was recorded at 0, 7th and 14 day. The hydro alcoholic extract of PHF was found to be safe up to 4000 mg/kg body weight. Hence from the present study it can be concluded that PHF at the limit dose of 4000 mg/kg body weight.

Effect of hydroalcoholic extract of Polyherbal Formulation on Body Weight and Atherogenic Index on Triton WR-1339 induced Hyperlipidemic rats.

Triton treated group showed significance increase ($P < 0.0001$) the levels of body weight and Atherogenic Index compared to normal group. Post-treatment with PHF and Atorvastatin at different doses (200mg/kg, 400mg/k.g. /b.w.) and 10 mg/k.g/b.w., significantly ($P < 0.001$) prevented the elevation of these parameter when compared to hyperlipidemic rats (Table-1).

Table 1: Effect of hydroalcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation on Body Weight and Atherogenic Index on Triton WR-1339 induced Hyperlipidemic rats.

Treatment Groups	Body Weight (gm)	Atherogenic Index (A.I.)
I. Normal Control	190.9±1.10	2.16±0.27
II. Triton Treated (Triton 200 mg/kg, i.v.)	209.2±1.53	7.12±0.38
III. Triton + PHF (200 mg/kg/p.o.)	199.1±0.92*	3.24±0.01**
IV. Triton + PHF (400 mg/kg/p.o.)	195.2±1.77**	2.93±0.06***
V. Triton + Atorvastatin (10mg/kg/p.o)	194.6±0.98***	2.73±0.05***

All the Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, n=6, value *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$ Compared to Drug and PHF treated groups to vs. Toxic Control (Triton)

Effect of hydroalcoholic extract of PHF on Serum Cholesterol, Triglyceride, HDL-C, LDL-C and VLDL-C in TritonWR-1339 induced Hyperlipidemic Rats

Total cholesterol and triglycerides levels were significantly increased in Triton WR-1339 injected rats as compared to normal control rats. Triton injected rats showed significance increase ($P < 0.0001$) the levels of TC, TG, LDL & VLDL compared to normal control group. Treatment with Poly Herbal Formulation, at different doses (200 mg/kg, 400mg/kg), significantly ($P < 0.001$) prevented the elevation of these parameters when compared to Triton induced hyperlipidemic rats. Treatment with PHF (200 and 400 mg/kg) caused a dose dependent changes in Total Cholesterol and Triglycerides (Table-2)

Table-2: Effect of hydroalcoholic extract of PHF on Serum Cholesterol, Triglyceride, HDL-C, LDL-C and VLDL-C on TritonWR-1339 induced Hyperlipidemic Rats.

Treatment Groups	Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	% Change	Triglyceride (mg/dL)	% Change	HDL (mg/dL)	LDL (mg/dL)	VLDL (mg/dL)
I Control (Normal Saline 0.9% w/v)	83.8 ± 6.70	0.98 ± 0.16	69.8 ± 4.22	1.016±0.22	45.17±1.14	65.91±2.49	16.9±0.27
II Triton Treated (Triton 200 mg/kg, i.v.)	294.4±17.1.8	-----	365.2 ± 23.73	-----	27.77±1.12	167±4.51	28.6±0.35
III Triton + PHF (200 mg/kg/p.o.)	208.4±26.632**	28.40±3.22**	285.3±27.65**	16.78 ± 2.42 *	41.26±0.82**	129±2.30***	25.38±0.55**
IV Triton + PHF (400 mg/kg/p.o.)	159.6±23.48*	49.30±2.66**	209.4±25.65**	42.16±2.30**	33.67±0.51*	116.6±2.13**	18.7±0.42*
V Triton + Atorvastatin 10mg/kg/p.o)	148.9±21.31*	46.29±1.61**	205.5±26.55**	41.17±2.28**	39.06±0.76**	118±2.14**	20.9±0.41*

TRI- Triton WR 1339 (200 mg/kg; i.v.); PHF – Poly Herbal Formulation

% change was calculated using formula % Change = $[(T_t - T_c) / T_c] \times 100$

Where in T_t = values of treated group and T_c = values of respective control group.

% change of PHF group is calculated with respect to control (Normal Saline) group,

While % change of TRI + PHF groups is calculated with respect to TRI group.

All the values are expressed as mean ± SEM, n=6, value *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$ and * $p < 0.05$ Drug and PHF treated group compared to Toxic control (Triton) group

DISCUSSION

Hyperlipidemia and Hypertriglyceridemia are important risk factors for diabetes-accelerated atherosclerosis. The main aim of treatment in patients with hyperlipidemia is to reduce the risk of developing ischemic heart disease or the occurrence of further cardiovascular or cerebrovascular complications [22]. Two common lipid abnormalities are characterized either by high blood cholesterol levels (hypercholesterolemia) or high blood levels of triglycerides (hypertriglyceridemia). Cholesterol is essential for the formation of cell membranes and the manufacture of several hormones, but it is not required from the diet because the liver produces all the cholesterol the body needs. High cholesterol can cause atherosclerosis, a dangerous accumulation of cholesterol and other deposits on the walls of the coronary arteries. These deposits (plaques) can reduce blood flow through your arteries, which can cause complications, such as heart attack, Carotid artery (Brain Stroke), chest pain (Angina) and other symptoms of coronary artery disease (Atherosclerosis). In addition, very high blood triglyceride levels can lead to inflammation of the pancreas (pancreatitis). Studies have shown that high cholesterol increases the risk for heart attack, stroke, circulation problems and death.

The non-ionic detergent, Triton WR-1339, has been widely used to block the uptake of triacylglycerol-rich lipoproteins from plasma by peripheral tissues in order to produce acute hyperlipidemia in animal models which are often used for a number of objectives, in particular for screening natural or chemical hypolipidemic drugs [23]. A single parenteral administration of Triton WR-1339 to adult rats produces a hyperlipidemia in which cholesterol, triglycerides and phospholipids increase to a maximum in about 20hrs and decrease thereafter. The majority of experimental evidence supports the concept that Triton physically alters very low density lipoproteins, rendering them refractive to the action of lipolytic enzymes of blood and tissues. This prevents or delays their removal from blood and secondarily stimulates the synthesis of lipid, enhancing the hyperlipidemia. In this communication we describe a screening test for hypolipidemic drugs in which the agents were administered orally to rats immediately following and 20 hr after intravenous injection of Triton, and activity was determined by measuring serum cholesterol and Triglycerides 43 hr post-Triton [24].

In our study, this model gave similar plasma lipid profile changes, at 24 h after Triton WR-1339 injection in rats. This result demonstrates the feasibility of using Triton induced hyperlipidemic rats as an experimental model to investigate the hypolipidemic effect of polyherbal extracts. In Our study clearly shows that the large increase in serum levels of cholesterol and triglycerides due to Triton WR-1339 injection results mostly from an increase of VLDL secretion by the liver accompanied by a strong reduction of VLDL and LDL catabolism. [25]. The reduction of total cholesterol by the hydro alcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation was associated with a decrease of its LDL fraction in serum and liver, which is the target of several hypolipidemic drugs. Report of a study suggests that cholesterol lowering activity of the hydroalcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation could be the result of the rapid catabolism of LDL cholesterol through its hepatic receptors for final elimination in the form of bile acids, as demonstrated [26]. Increased level of serum LDL-cholesterol results in increased risk for the development of atherosclerosis [27]. It is well known that HDL-Cholesterol levels have a protective role in coronary artery disease [28]. HDL-cholesterol is reported to have a preventive function against atherogenesis since an independent inverse relationship between blood HDL-C levels and cardiovascular risk incidence has been reported [29]. The hydroalcoholic extract of our polyherbal formulation also increased HDL-cholesterol levels thus exhibiting antihyperlipidemic action. Atherosclerotic index (A.I) is believed to be an important risk factor for diagnosis of atherosclerosis. The hydro alcoholic extract of our polyherbal formulation reduced atherogenic index which is one of the most important risk factors of atherosclerotic plaques. Similar results were reported by others when studying the hypolipidemic effect of natural products. [30].

A polyherbal formulation containing hydroalcoholic extracts of the three herbs (viz. *Holostemma annularis* (Asclepiadaceae), *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Boraginaceae) and *Anogeissus latifolia* (Combretaceae). The ingredients in the formulation have been reported to possess the leaves, heartwood, roots and bark. *Anogeissus latifolia* plant is traditionally used for the treatment of dysentery, snakebite, leprosy, wounds and ulcers, skin diseases, jaundice and diabetes. [31]. The roots of *Holostemma annularis* are useful in ophthalmopathy, orchitis, cough, burning sensation, stomachalgia, constipation, fever and tridoshas. The roots is also used in spermatorrhoea and reported to possess cooling, tonic and lactative properties [32&33]. *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Boraginaceae) reported as a medicinal herb widely used in traditional system of medicine to treat dysentery, snake bite and urinary diseases. It is useful in vitiated conditions of *Vata* and *Kapha*, arthralgia, inflammations, dyspepsia, diarrhoea, dysentery, leprosy and skin diseases [34, 35, 36 & 37].

Thus, the presence of flavinoids, tannins, phenols, steroids, saponins, rutin, quercetin and β -sitosterol in polyherbal formulation maybe the contributing factor towards its anti-hypercholesterolemia effect and justifies the folkloric use of these plants. The results presented in this study indicated that the hydroalcoholic extract of polyherbal formulation at doses of 200mg & 400mg, post treatment decreases the Triton Wr-1339 induced increased levels of total cholesterol, TGs, LDL, VLDL and increases HDL Levels. Among these two doses 400mg, decreases the lipid parameters more significantly than the 200 mg, hence the higher dose is more protective than the lower dose. Lowering high cholesterol levels significantly reduce the risk of heart attacks, strokes and death.

CONCLUSION

The antihyperlipidemic effect of a polyherbal formulation containing hydroalcoholic extracts of *Anogeissus latifolia* (Combretaceae), *Holostemma annularis* (Asclepiadaceae) and *Trichodesma amplexicaule* (Boraginaceae) showed dose dependent antihyperlipidemic action against Triton WR-1339 induced hyperlipidemia. The lipid lowering effect of hydroalcoholic extract of PHF is probable mechanism may be due to its antioxidant, free radical scavenging activity. Some bioactive compounds like Terpenoids, Tannins, β - Sitosterol, Lupeol, Phenols and Flavonoids may ameliorating the biohazards induced by hypercholesterolemia in *Wistar* rats at both molecular and cellular levels. The results are encouraging enough for further studies aimed at understanding the mechanism of action and identify the bioactive compounds.

CONFLICT OF INTRESTS

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interests.

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